
Labelling of the ACTRIS National Facilities operating Aerosol Remote Sensing instruments

Emitter	CARS & ARES
Version	01
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Table of contents

APPLICABILITY OF THE DOCUMENT	3
ACRONYMS.....	3
REFERENCE DOCUMENTS.....	3
1 INTRODUCTION	4
2 GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS	5
3 LABELLING OF THE ACTRIS AEROSOL REMOTE SENSING OBSERVATIONAL PLATFORMS	6
3.1 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES.....	6
3.2 LABELLING STEP-BY-STEP	6
3.2.1 <i>Step1a Initial acceptance</i>	6
3.2.2 <i>Step1b Performance evaluation</i>	7
3.2.3 <i>Step1c Approval</i>	7
3.2.4 <i>Step2 Annual performance evaluation</i>	8
4 LABELLING OF ACTRIS MOBILE PLATFORMS EMBEDDING AEROSOL REMOTE SENSING INSTRUMENTS...9	9
4.1 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES.....	9
4.2 LABELLING STEP-BY-STEP	9
4.2.1 <i>Step1a Initial acceptance</i>	9
4.2.2 <i>Step1b Performance evaluation</i>	10
4.2.3 <i>Step1c Approval</i>	10
4.2.4 <i>Step2 Annual performance evaluation</i>	11
5 EVALUATION OF ACTRIS AEROSOL REMOTE SENSING OBSERVATIONAL PLATFORMS	12
5.1 REQUIREMENTS FOR BEING ACTRIS COMPLIANT	12
5.2 IMPLICATIONS OF A FAILED EVALUATION	12
6 EVALUATION OF ACTRIS MOBILE PLATFORMS EMBEDDING AEROSOL REMOTE SENSING INSTRUMENTS .	14
6.1 REQUIREMENTS FOR BEING ACTRIS COMPLIANT	14
6.2 METHODOLOGY FOR CALCULATION OF THE DATA COVERAGE	14
6.3 IMPLICATIONS OF A FAILED EVALUATION	15
ANNEX 1 TEMPLATE FOR THE ANNUAL EVALUATION OF NF PERFORMANCE (STEP1B / STEP2 OF THE LABELLING)	16
ANNEX 2 TEMPLATE FOR THE LONG-TERM EVALUATION OF NF PERFORMANCE (STEP1C / AT EACH 5 YEARS IN STEP2 OF THE LABELLING)	18

Applicability of the document

These guidelines apply to the ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing National Facilities.

Acronyms

- ACTRIS - Aerosol, Clouds and Trace gases Research InfraStructure
- ACTRIS GA – ACTRIS General Assembly
- ARES – Aerosol Remote Sensing unit of the ACTRIS Data Centre
- ARS – Aerosol Remote Sensing
- CARPORT – CARS workflow management portal
- CARS - Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing
- CLU – Cloud Remote Sensing unit of the ACTRIS Data Centre
- CCRES - Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing
- DC – Data Centre
- MP – Mobile Platform
- NF - National Facility
- NRT – Near-real time (less than 3 days from the measurements)
- OP – Observational Platform
- PI – Principal Investigator
- RI Comm – Research Infrastructure Committee
- RRT – Real-real time (less than 3 hours from the measurement)
- SCC – Single Calculus Chain

Reference documents

- [1]. [Documentation on technical concepts and requirements for ACTRIS Observational Platforms](#)
- [2]. [ACTRIS NF Labelling Plan](#)
- [3]. [Descriptions of the workflows between ACTRIS components](#)
- [4]. [ACTRIS Data Management Plan](#)
- [5]. [CARS implementation plan](#)
- [6]. [ACTRIS vocabulary](#)
- [7]. ACTRIS principles for evaluating data provision, service provision and QA/QC
- [8]. Technical requirements for ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms
- [9]. Technical requirements for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating aerosol high-power lidars
- [10]. Technical requirements for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer
- [11]. Measurement Guidelines for aerosol high-power lidars
- [12]. Measurement Guidelines for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers
- [13]. Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
- [14]. Standard Operation Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer
- [15]. Quality Assurance Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
- [16]. Quality Assurance Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer

1 Introduction

Aerosol remote sensing instruments as considered by ACTRIS are:

- a) aerosol high-power lidars;
- b) automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers;
- c) automatic low-power lidars and ceilometers.

ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing National Facilities operate aerosol high-power lidars and automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers.

Note: The guidelines in this document do not apply to automatic low-power lidars / ceilometers which are currently operated as part of the ACTRIS Cloud Remote Sensing National Facilities

ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing National Facilities operate aerosol remote sensing instruments either as Observational Platforms (at fixed site) or as part of a Mobile Platform (movable).

Note: Aerosol remote sensing instruments can also be operated by the EARLINET (aerosol high-power lidars), AERONET (automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers) and E-PROFILE (automatic low-power lidars and ceilometers). The guidelines in this document do not apply to EARLINET, AERONET and E-PROFILE stations which are not part of ACTRIS.

In order to be labelled as ACTRIS Facility, both the Observational Platforms and the Mobile Platforms must undergo the labelling process. This document describes the labelling process for ACTRIS National Facilities which operate aerosol remote sensing instruments (OPs and MPs).

- Considerations applicable to all ACTRIS National Facilities which operate aerosol remote sensing instruments (OPs and MPs) are presented in [Section 2](#).
- Specific roles and responsibilities, conditions to be met and actions to be pursued for the labelling of ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms are described in [Section 3](#).
- Specific roles and responsibilities, conditions to be met and actions to be pursued for the labelling of ACTRIS Mobile Platforms embedding aerosol remote sensing instruments are described in [Section 4](#).
- Principles for the evaluation of ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms are described in [Section 5](#).
- Principles for the evaluation of ACTRIS Mobile Platforms embedding aerosol remote sensing instruments are described in [Section 6](#).

2 General considerations

The main responsibility of CARS and ARES is to provide operation support to ACTRIS ARS National Facilities. This operation support extends from the calibration of instruments to the fully quality assured data products, which are calculated from a single instrument and/or from synergy of multiple instruments.

ACTRIS National Facilities (OPs and MPs) must be labelled according to ACTRIS' criteria. The labelling process includes: a) an initial technical evaluation to enter the labelling process; b) support from the corresponding Topical Centre and Data Centre Unit to implement the necessary upgrades, procedures, tools and processing chains; c) evaluation of performances for granting the label; d) annual evaluation of performances.

Data provided to the ACTRIS Data Centre by the ACTRIS National Facilities are tagged as:

- "ACTRIS compliant data" if all technical requirements are met (including synergy of instruments), the associated SOPs and QAPs issued by CARS are followed, and the data is submitted to the ACTRIS Data Centre according to the measurement guidelines;
- "ACTRIS labelled data" as soon as the ACTRIS label is granted.

ACTRIS labelling process is schematically presented below:

Figure 1 Steps and actions of the ACTRIS labelling process: responsibilities and interactions

The performances of the ACTRIS National Facilities are annually evaluated according to the specific ACTRIS' criteria, starting with the initial acceptance and throughout the entire lifetime of the ACTRIS National Facility.

At least 24 months of compliant data submitted to the ACTRIS Data Centre are required in order for the facility to be granted the ACTRIS label. The label can be withdrawn at the decision of the ACTRIS General Assembly if the facility is negatively evaluated for several years.

Underlying principles for evaluating data provision, service provision and QA/QC of ACTRIS National Facilities are described in [ACTRIS principles for evaluating data provision, service provision and QA/QC](#)

3 Labelling of the ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms

3.1 Roles and responsibilities

Country delegate / NCP – proposes NFs and components

OP PI – coordinates the activities of all OP components; contact person for ACTRIS HO; fills in the necessary information in the **ACTRIS labelling portal** (<https://actris-nf-labelling.out.ocp.fmi.fi/>)

ARS PI – coordinates the activities related to ARS instruments and variables; contact person for CARS and ARES; fills in the necessary information in **CARPORT, the CARS workflow management portal** (<https://carport.inoe.ro/>)

CARS – provides support for the QA/QC of the measurements performed by the ARS NF; evaluates the compliance with the technical requirements in the various steps of the labelling; evaluates the overall performances of the OP and recommends to the RI Comm granting the initial acceptance / label

ARES – provides support for the data processing and the QA/QC of the data products derived from the measurements performed by the ARS NF; evaluates the compliance with the measurement guidelines in the various steps of the labelling

RI Comm – recommends granting the initial acceptance / label

ACTRIS GA – approves the label

3.2 Labelling step-by-step

3.2.1 Step1a Initial acceptance

Conditions to be met:

- The OP should have been proposed by the country as operating an Aerosol Remote Sensing component
- The ARS OP should have a realistic plan for becoming fully compliant with the ACTRIS ARS requirements in max. 2 years after the initial acceptance (upgrade plan)
- The ARS OP should have the institutional commitment to operate the facility at least for the next 5 years after the initial acceptance

Actions to be done:

1. The PI of the OP must inform ACTRIS HO about the readiness of the ARS component to enter the labelling process
2. The PI of the OP must fill in the information about the ARS component in the ACTRIS labelling portal
 - Name and contact of the ARS PI
 - List of ARS instruments operated by the facility
3. The ARS PI must fill in the technical information about the ARS instruments in CARPORT
 - The ARS PI must activate his/her CARPORT user (notification from CARPORT)
 - The ARS PI must fill in technical information about the ARS instruments in CARPORT and submit the application (notification from CARPORT)
 - The ARS PI must read the preliminary report from CARS and upload the upgrade plan in CARPORT to respond to CARS' recommendations (notification from CARPORT)
4. The PI of the OP must upload the upgrade plan and the commitment letter for the ARS OP in the ACTRIS labelling portal

5. CARS must upload the technical reports in the ACTRIS labelling portal
6. The RI Comm must grant the initial acceptance for the ARS OP
7. The ACTRIS HO must send the initial acceptance certificate to the PI of the OP.

3.2.2 *Step1b Performance evaluation*

Conditions to be met:

- The ARS OP should have been initially accepted

Actions to be done:

- The ARS OP must implement the necessary upgrades to meet the technical requirements stated in the Technical requirements for ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms
- The ARS OP must implement the SOPs:
 - o Operate the photometer according to Standard Operation Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer
 - o Operate the lidar according to Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
 - o Maintain and update the lidar log according to Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
 - o Implement and use ATLAS for lidar measurements quality control according to Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
- The ARS OP must participate in the QA/QC activities:
 - o Calibrate the photometer according to Quality Assurance Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer
 - o Perform and submit to CARS lidar QA tests according to Quality Assurance Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
 - o Perform routine QC actions on monthly basis according to [Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars](#)
 - o Implement recommendations from CARS to optimize the performances of the instruments
 - o Participate to site audits / direct comparisons as necessary
 - o Participate to webinars, workshops and training sessions
- The ARS OP must collect and submit compliant data to the ACTRIS Data Centre:
 - o Perform and submit photometer measurements according to Measurement Guidelines for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers
 - o Perform and submit lidar measurements according to [Measurement Guidelines for aerosol high-power lidars](#)
- CARS collects information from ARES and submits to the ACTRIS HO the annual performance evaluation for the ARS OP.

3.2.3 *Step1c Approval*

Conditions to be met:

- The ARS OP should have been initially accepted
- The ARS OP should have been obtained, for two consecutive years, positive evaluations

Actions to be done:

1. CARS must inform the ACTRIS HO about the compliance of the ARS OP in view of the approval of the label
2. The RI Comm must grant the label for the ARS OP
3. The ACTRIS HO must send the label certificate to the PI of the OP.

3.2.4 Step2 Annual performance evaluation

Conditions to be met:

- The ARS OP should have been labelled

Actions to be done:

1. The ARS OP must operate according to the SOPs:
 - Operate the photometer according to Standard Operation Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer
 - Operate the lidar according to the Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
 - Maintain and update the lidar log according to the Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
 - Use ATLAS for lidar measurements quality control according to [Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars](#)
2. The ARS OP must participate in the QA/QC activities:
 - Calibrate the photometer according to Quality Assurance Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer
 - Perform and submit to CARS lidar QA tests according to Quality Assurance Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
 - Perform routine QC actions on monthly basis according to [Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars](#)
 - Implement recommendations from CARS to optimize the performances of the instruments
 - Participate to site audits / direct comparisons as necessary
 - Participate to webinars, workshops and training sessions
3. The ARS OP must collect and submit compliant data to the ACTRIS Data Centre:
 - Perform and submit photometer measurements according to Measurement Guidelines for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers
 - Perform and submit lidar measurements according to Measurement Guidelines for aerosol high-power lidars
5. CARS collects information from ARES and submits to the ACTRIS HO the annual performance evaluation for the ARS OP

4 Labelling of ACTRIS Mobile Platforms embedding aerosol remote sensing instruments

4.1 Roles and responsibilities

Country delegate / NCP – proposes NFs and components

NF PI – coordinates the activities of all NF components; contact person for ACTRIS HO; fills in the necessary information in the **ACTRIS labelling portal** (<https://actris-nf-labelling.out.ocp.fmi.fi/>)

ARS PI – coordinates the activities related to ARS instruments and variables; contact person for CARS and ARES; fills in the necessary information in CARPORT, the **CARS workflow management portal** (<https://carport.inoe.ro/>)

CARS – provides support for the QA/QC of the measurements performed by the MP; evaluates the compliance of the aerosol remote sensing instruments against the technical requirements in the various steps of the labelling

ARES – provides support for the data processing and the QA/QC of the data products derived from the aerosol remote sensing measurements performed by the MP; evaluates the compliance of the aerosol remote sensing data against the measurement guidelines in the various steps of the labelling

Mobile Platform Labelling Group – evaluates the overall performances of the MP and recommends to the RI Comm granting the initial acceptance / label

RI Comm – recommends granting the initial acceptance / label

ACTRIS GA – approves the label

4.2 Labelling step-by-step

4.2.1 Step1a Initial acceptance

Conditions to be met:

- The MP should have been proposed by the country and should include at least one aerosol remote sensing instrument
- The MP should have a realistic plan for becoming fully compliant with the ACTRIS requirements in max. 2 years after the initial acceptance (upgrade plan)
- The MP should have the institutional commitment to operate the facility at least for the next 5 years after the initial acceptance

Actions to be done:

1. The PI of the MP must inform ACTRIS HO about the readiness of the MP to enter the labelling process
2. The PI of the MP must fill in the information about the ARS instrument(s) in the ACTRIS labelling portal
 - Name and contact of the PI for the ARS instruments onboard of the MP
 - List of ARS instruments onboard of the MP
3. The PI for the ARS instruments onboard of the MP must fill in the technical information about the ARS instruments in CARPORT
 - The PI for the ARS instruments onboard of the MP must activate his/her CARPORT user (notification from CARPORT)

- The PI for the ARS instruments onboard of the MP must fill in technical information about the ARS instruments in CARPORT and submit the application (notification from CARPORT)
- The PI for the ARS instruments onboard of the MP must read the preliminary report from CARS and upload the upgrade plan in CARPORT to respond to CARS' recommendations (notification from CARPORT)
- 4. CARS must send the technical reports to the Mobile Platform Labelling Group
- 5. The Mobile Platform Labelling Group must upload the overall report in the ACTRIS labelling portal
- 6. The RI Comm must grant the initial acceptance for the MP
- 7. The ACTRIS HO must send the initial acceptance certificate to the PI of the MP.

4.2.2 *Step1b Performance evaluation*

Conditions to be met:

- The MP should have been initially accepted

Actions to be done:

1. The MP must implement the necessary upgrades to meet the technical requirements stated in the Technical requirements for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating aerosol high-power lidars
2. The MP must implement the SOPs corresponding to the ARS instruments onboard of the MP:
 - Operate the photometer according to Standard Operation Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer
 - Operate the lidar according to Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
 - Maintain and update the lidar log according to [Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars](#)
 - Implement and use ATLAS for lidar measurements quality control according to [Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars](#)
3. The MP must participate in the QA/QC activities corresponding to the ARS instruments onboard of the MP:
 - Calibrate the photometer according to Quality Assurance Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer
 - Perform and submit to CARS lidar QA tests according to Quality Assurance Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
 - Implement recommendations from CARS to optimize the performances of the instruments
 - Participate to site audits / direct comparisons as necessary
 - Participate to webinars, workshops and training sessions
4. The MP must collect and submit compliant data to the ACTRIS Data Centre:
 - Perform and submit photometer measurements according to Measurement Guidelines for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers
 - Perform and submit lidar measurements according to Measurement Guidelines for aerosol high-power lidars
5. CARS collects information from ARES and submits to the ACTRIS HO the annual performance evaluation for the ARS instruments onboard of the MP

4.2.3 *Step1c Approval*

Conditions to be met:

- The MP should have been initially accepted
- The MP should have been obtained, for two consecutive years, positive evaluations

Actions to be done:

1. CARS must inform the ACTRIS HO about the compliance of the ARS instruments onboard of the MP, in view of the approval of the label
2. The RI Comm must grant the label for the MP
3. The ACTRIS HO must send the label certificate to the PI of the MP

4.2.4 Step2 Annual performance evaluation

Conditions to be met:

- The MP should have been labelled

Actions to be done:

1. The MP must operate according to the SOPs corresponding to the ARS instruments onboard of the MP:
 - Operate the photometer according to Standard Operation Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer
 - Operate the lidar according to Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
 - Maintain and update the lidar log according to Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
 - Use ATLAS for lidar measurements quality control
2. The MP must participate in the QA/QC activities corresponding to the ARS instruments onboard of the MP:
 - Calibrate the photometer according to Quality Assurance Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer
 - Perform and submit to CARS lidar QA tests according to Quality Assurance Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
 - Implement recommendations from CARS to optimize the performances of the instruments
 - Participate to site audits / direct comparisons as necessary
 - Participate to webinars, workshops and training sessions
3. The MP must collect and submit compliant data to the ACTRIS Data Centre:
 - Perform and submit photometer measurements according to Measurement Guidelines for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers
 - Perform and submit lidar measurements according to Measurement Guidelines for aerosol high-power lidars
4. CARS collects information from ARES and submits to the ACTRIS HO the annual performance evaluation for the ARS instruments onboard of the MP

5 Evaluation of ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms

5.1 Requirements for being ACTRIS compliant

The facility should submit to the ACTRIS Data Centre data collected in accordance with ACTRIS procedures and complying with the requirements on average of at least 75% of the expected time coverage during the evaluation period, excluding times when the instrument cannot measure. This is calculated as covered time for each parameter separately and averaged over all mandatory parameters so that insufficient data provision on one parameter may be compensated by other parameters. The times when an instrument cannot measure due to reasons not under control of the facility are to be excluded from the calculation of any parameter for which the instrument is needed.

Note: The measurement schedule, workflow for the data provision and the variables associated to aerosol high-power lidars, as well as the methodology for calculating data coverage for the lidar-related variables at stationary station are described in Measurement Guidelines for aerosol high-power lidars.

Note: The measurement schedule, workflow for the data provision and the variables associated to automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers, as well as the methodology for calculating data coverage for the photometer-related variables at stationary stations are described in Measurement Guidelines for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers.

Note: For being granted with the ACTRIS label, additional conditions apply, i.e. the Observational Platforms must submit at least 24 months of compliant data to the ACTRIS Data Centre, within 3 consecutive years out of the maximum 5 years after the initial acceptance.

The instruments must participate in the QA/QC activities according to the schedule provided by CARS. If the instrument cannot participate in a given QA/QC action as scheduled, it may request CARS for re-scheduling, ideally during the same year. The special cases of instruments in hard-to-reach locations will be considered. If an instrument does not participate in a required QA/QC activity during the year, the data produced by the instrument is to be considered non-compliant starting from the beginning of the next year.

Note: The mandatory QA/QC activities for ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms are described in Technical requirements for ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms.

Note: The mandatory QA/QC activities for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating aerosol high-power lidars are described in Technical requirements for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating aerosol high-power lidars.

Note: The mandatory QA/QC activities for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers are described in Technical requirements for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer.

5.2 Implications of a failed evaluation

If the facility-component is evaluated as not compliant with ACTRIS requirements, the outcome depends on the state of the labelling process it is in:

In labelling step 1b, before the full label is granted, the component may be non-compliant in the beginning, as it might be still ongoing implementation. A facility is required to provide at least 24 months of compliant data (of all mandatory variables) during 3 consecutive years, before it can receive

the full label (labelling step 1c, by ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly), and this is expected to happen within 5 years from the initial acceptance. The labelling status will be marked in the meta data of the files in the DC, as data sets not fully labelled will be available for users, but not with ACTRIS NF label (ACTRIS compliant or ACTRIS associated if the data are not ACTRIS compliant). If the 5-year time is exceeded, further actions will be decided by the Head Office (HO) after consulting the NF, CARS and ARES.

In Step2, after the component has received the full label, a single failure in the annual compliancy evaluation will not remove the label, but corrective actions need to be planned and taken together with the respective TC or DC and reported and notified to the Head Office. After two consecutive years of failing the evaluation, the situation will be examined in detail and the component might be brought to the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly for decision whether the label is to be removed.

6 Evaluation of ACTRIS Mobile Platforms embedding aerosol remote sensing instruments

6.1 Requirements for being ACTRIS compliant

Access provision is mandatory to mobile platforms. Access is to be evaluated based on the time available for access, not for the actual access provided, as that depends on the users' interest towards the facility and quality of applications, both outside the power of the NF. The time periods needed for preparing the access use and returning the platform to its default state are to be included as access time in the calculation.

The facility should submit campaign data to the ACTRIS Data Centre data collected in accordance with ACTRIS procedures and complying with the requirements

Note: The workflow for the data provision and the variables associated to aerosol high-power lidars are described in Measurement Guidelines for aerosol high-power lidars.

Note: The workflow for the data provision and the variables associated to automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers are described in Measurement Guidelines for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers.

Note: For being granted with the ACTRIS label, additional conditions may apply. To be developed later, based on ACTRIS general principles for compliancy of Mobile Platforms

The instruments must participate in the QA/QC activities according to the schedule provided by CARS. If the instrument cannot participate in a given QA/QC action as scheduled, it may request CARS for re-scheduling, ideally during the same year. The special cases of instruments in hard-to-reach locations will be considered. If an instrument does not participate in a required QA/QC activity during the year, the data produced by the instrument is to be considered non-compliant starting from the beginning of the next year.

Note: The mandatory QA/QC activities for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating aerosol high-power lidars are described in Technical requirements for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating aerosol high-power lidars.

Note: The mandatory QA/QC activities for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers are described in Technical requirements for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer.

6.2 Methodology for calculation of the data coverage

The schedule in case of Mobile platforms is defined by the user according to the objectives of the campaign / experiment. Mobile Platform data will flow in the ACTRIS ARES Data Centre and will be made publicly available (embargo period can apply in some specific cases).

It is expected that **at least 1 DOI should be released for each measurement campaign.** However, the Mobile Platform Principle Investigator can request more DOI releases to ARES motivating the choice.

Note: In order to obtain the data DOI release from ARES, the Mobile Platform Principle Investigator should contact ARES and provide all needed information.

Note: In case of campaigns extending for more than 1 year, DOI should be obtained for each calendar year.

The equation for calculating the data coverage (percentage) over the evaluation period is:

$$\%Datacoverage = \frac{No. of DOIs}{No. of campaigns}$$

6.3 Implications of a failed evaluation

To be developed later, based on ACTRIS general principles for compliancy of Mobile Platforms.

Annex 1 Template for the annual evaluation of NF performance (Step1b / Step2 of the labelling)

ACTRIS National Facility annual performance evaluation

Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platform

NF short name

NF information

Component PI (name & contact): Name & Surname, email address
Start date of ACTRIS compliance for the entire component: Month Year¹
Date of initial acceptance: Month Year
Date of full label (if is the case): Month Year

Summary report year: YYYY

Report issued by	TC name; DC unit name	
Time period covered by the report	DD/MM/YYYY - DD/MM/YYYY	
Date of the report	DD/MM/YYYY	
Performance related to data provision	Status of the data provision during the evaluation period	Choose an item.
Performance related to instrument calibration	Status of the instruments' calibration during the evaluation period	Choose an item.
General performance statement	Choose an item.	

CF recommendation

Free text (including the possibility to be recommended for Step1c or for withdrawal of the label in near future)

¹ Month of the TC technical evaluation report
22 December 2025

Report

Data provision

Status of the data provision	Statement	Comment
Has the NF providing data?	Choose an item.	
Were all mandatory variables provided?	Choose an item.	
Were the NRT variables provided?	Choose an item.	
Were there gaps in the measurements?	Choose an item.	

Instrumentation

Status of the data provision	Statement	Comment
Has the NF participated to calibrations, training sessions and QA workshops?	Choose an item.	
Has the NF implemented the operation and quality assurance procedures (including calibrations) for all involved instruments?	Choose an item.	
Has the NF implemented the software tools provided by the TC?	Choose an item.	
Has the NF faced failures or technical problems with the instruments?	Choose an item.	

Other considerations

Write here other relevant things, if any: how experienced the team is, how constant the data provision is, if the TC has concerns or not.

References

Reference to the relevant documents (e.g. guidelines, requirements, etc.)

Annex 2 Template for the long-term evaluation of NF performance (Step1c / at each 5 years in Step2 of the labelling)

ACTRIS National Facility long-term performance evaluation

Aerosol Remote Sensing *Observational Platform*

NF short name

NF information

Component PI (name & contact): Name & Surname, email address
Start date of ACTRIS compliance for the entire component: Month Year²
Date of initial acceptance: Month Year
Date of full label (if is the case): Month Year

Summary report on compliance year(s): start year – end year

Report issued by	TC name & DC unit name	
Time period covered by the report	DD/MM/YYYY - DD/MM/YYYY	
Date of the report	DD/MM/YYYY	
Data compliance	XX months with compliant data out of total XX months during the evaluation period	Choose an item.
Instrument compliance	Calibration of instruments	Choose an item.
General compliance	Choose an item.	according to requirements for the XXX component.

CF recommendation

Choose an item.

² Month of the TC technical evaluation report
22 December 2025

Detailed report

Data provision

Variable name	Variable type (mandatory / optional)	Associated instrument	No. of months of compliant data during the evaluation period	Data coverage (% of total expected) during the evaluation period ³	Compliance with ACTRIS requirements (Yes / No)
Summary for all mandatory variables			X	XX%	Choose an item.
Variable 1	M / O	Instrument associated to variable 1	X	XX%	Choose an item.
Variable 2	M / O	Instrument associated to variable 2	X	XX%	Choose an item.
.....					
Variable n	M / O	Instrument associated to variable n	X	XX%	Choose an item.

Insert here time span of number of datasets submitted, and % data coverage for instrument/variable 1	Insert here time span of number of datasets submitted, and % data coverage for instrument/variable 2
Figure 1 Graphical representation of instrument/variable 1 data submission during the concerned time period (number of datasets per month / % of total expected per month)	Figure 2 Graphical representation of instrument/variable 2 data submission during the concerned time period (number of daily datasets per month / % of total expected per month).

..... (Multiply the table above for all instruments/variables and refresh the number of the caption.)

General comments regarding data submission:

Write here a short description of the environmental conditions (if relevant), continuity and timeliness of data submission.

- **In case of recommendations to be promoted to Step1c**, if not all mandatory variables fulfil the 24 months requirement please explain here why an exception should be made.
- **In case of recommendation to withdraw the label**, please refer to negative performance related to data provision in the previous years.

³ Calculated for the months of compliant data during the calendar year (months with zero datasets to be excluded if not reported as exceptions e.g. due to weather, instrument failure or instrument deployed for calibration)

Instrumentation

Instrument type	Instrument PID (if available)	Instrument landing page (link if available)	Latest passed calibration / intercomparison (date)	Next required calibration / intercomparison (year)	Compliance with ACTRIS requirements (Yes / No)
Instrument 1	XXX	Link	DD/MM/YYYY	YYYY	Yes/No
Instrument 2	XXX	Link	DD/MM/YYYY	YYYY	Yes/No
.....					
Instrument n	XXX	Link	DD/MM/YYYY	YYYY	Yes/No

General comments regarding QA/QC of the instruments:

Write here a short general statement related to participation to the QA/QC program.

- **In case of recommendations to be promoted to Step1c**, describe here shortly, for each instrument: implementation of operation and quality assurance procedures, implementation of software tools provided by the TC, failures or technical problems faced, participation to calibrations, participation to training sessions and QA workshops.
- **In case of recommendation to withdraw the label**, please refer to negative performance related to instrument calibrations in the previous years.

Other considerations

Write here other relevant things, if any: how experienced the team is, how constant the data provision is, if the TC has concerns or not. This part is summarizing in words the general compliance, and is justifying the recommendation.

References

Reference to the document describing requirements and methodology for the calculation of % data coverage